

Explainable Artificial Intelligence Bundles for Algorithm Lifecycle Management in the Manufacturing Domain

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Abstract— Lack of understanding for machine learning models’ inner workings by business users inevitably leads to lack of trust, particularly in critical operations. Recent advancements in artificial intelligence include the development of explainability methods and tools for machine learning and deep learning models. These explainable AI (XAI) techniques can significantly reduce the black box effect that often hinders direct inclusion and automated integration of ML outputs in decision making. The manufacturing sector is gradually increasing its adoption of AI-enabled systems, a process accelerated in the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, strengthening the need for explainability and robust XAI pipelines. This paper presents a framework of processes and tools designed and developed to bring the benefits of explainability in AI-enabled decision making in the manufacturing domain, providing the mechanisms to create production ready, trustful machine learning processes that foster collaboration among stakeholders coming from both business and technical backgrounds.

Keywords—explainability, data model, XAI, manufacturing

I. INTRODUCTION (*MOTIVATION, CONTEXT, OBJECTIVES*)

AI-enabled services, including those powered by machine learning, have been gradually increasing across numerous platforms, tools and applications around the world, impacting a broad range of industries, among which the manufacturing sector. Notwithstanding these advancements, incorporating machine learning outcomes into decision making remains challenging when critical operations are involved. Recent advancements in ML include explainability methods aiming to bridge the gap between the theoretical -yet undeniable-potential of artificial intelligence and its application, but effort is now required in order to bring these new technologies into the manufacturing processes responsible for the design, delivery and monitoring of employed ML algorithms [1].

Traceable AI Model Lifecycle Management is needed from the first steps of the creation of AI pipelines to their evaluation and deployment; from keeping track of the different experiments (features, model parameters and evaluation metrics, such as confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall, F1) to automating the final pipelines’

deployment in multiple environments (cloud or local, at the manufacturers’ premises) and running many models in parallel; from enabling collaboration among data scientists to collaboration among data scientists, data engineers and business experts to validate the models and maximise performance.

It is becoming clear that developing and leveraging robust and insightful AI pipelines that can assist manufacturers in their everyday operations and decision-making processes, spans well beyond ML models’ training by data scientists working in isolation. The vastness and complexity of functionalities and infrastructures that surround the pure ML code when it comes to building a solid ML system is highlighted in [2] where ML code lies at the center of twelve other ML system elements including data verification, process management, feature engineering, monitoring, model analysis, testing and debugging among others.

The present paper presents the challenges of bringing state of the art AI methods and tools into production-ready AI pipelines tailored to the manufacturing domain and proposes a framework of processes and tools that will help bring explainable and collaborative AI pipelines into the everyday operations of the manufacturing sector in a trustworthy manner.

II. EXISTING THEORIES & PREVIOUS WORK (LITERATURE REVIEW)

In order to design and implement the mechanisms that will allow the creation, configuration and application of XAI pipelines in the manufacturing domain, a landscape analysis is first performed both in terms of (a) theoretical foundations, good practices and reusable methods and (b) practical/technical building blocks that can be leveraged in the development process. This section presents the main findings from this analysis which spans across the numerous axes affecting the development and management of the pipelines. These axes are non-orthogonal due to the various interactions, dependencies and feedback loops inherent to the lifecycle of AI pipelines, and can be roughly grouped under the following areas:

- Data manipulation in the context of AI pipelines, which considers the data preprocessing, cleaning and transformation processes needed to bring the initial raw data to the appropriate form to be used for insights extraction, either through visualisations or used in ML models development and application. Data preparation has been a long-standing challenge in data science to avoid incorrect results and misleading conclusions obtained from inaccurate and coarse data [3], and there is an abundance of literature work, but also tools and libraries in numerous programming languages that provide such functionalities.

- Machine learning, which lies at the core of the AI bundles and concerns all functionalities around configuring, training, tuning and applying machine learning models but also model explainability which we want to be inherently part of the developed ML processes. Machine Learning is a domain covering a wide spectrum of theories, methods and applications both in terms of academic literature and implemented solutions. Explainability is however a relatively new aspect, and landscape analysis therefore focuses on the design principles to follow in order to provide a framework for building and deploying pipelines that will support – or even enforce - it by design.

- Visualisation and visual exploration, which is not limited here to the traditional definition of data visualisation. Instead, aspects of interest also evolve around model visualisations and examine how different visualisation functionalities can be leveraged across the steps of AI pipelines development, depending on the problem at hand and the stakeholder who needs the respective visual representation.

- MLOps, which constitute the intersection between ML and DevOps (development operations) and offer practices for building, deploying and managing Machine Learning (ML) systems.

Delivering and managing XAI pipelines entails a wide spectrum of processes, extending beyond the aforementioned – and already broad – fields. Orchestration engines and execution infrastructures, experiment tracking engines etc., are inevitably examined since relevant functionalities will be part of the XAI bundles, but the focus lies on the main drivers that will shape our solution towards the provision of the collaborative and by design explainable AI bundles for the manufacturing domain, which are discussed below.

A. Explainability

Lack of trust which stems from lack of understanding, further reinforced by the detachment of the ML solution development process which is commonly the case when it comes to people involved in decision-making vs those responsible for the ML solution development, can lead to hesitation in applying machine learning models more widely in everyday operations. Despite the impressive accuracies that can be achieved by machine learning models, it is vital that the inner workings and reasoning are transparent for the stakeholders that need to trust their outputs. Most machine learning and deep learning models are considered as “black box” models, due to their complexity. This mainly arises from their inherent non-linear capabilities, multiple parameters and complex transformations [4]. Furthermore, training over large datasets can make it difficult to understand which portion of the data has shaped the model output. These challenges have resulted in a lack of trust in the models and their predictions.

To address this clear industry need, new methods for the interpretation of machine learning models are published at breakneck speed [5][6]. ML model explainability (or interpretability) refers to the ability to explain what happens to the ML model between input and output; how it makes decisions, and why. Compliance with company policies, industry standards and government regulations are also among the benefits explainability can offer. Explainability can also help model performance, as it allows data scientists to understand how the model works, thus assisting in the optimization of its parameters. Libraries for global and local model-agnostic methods (e.g., Shap, Lime) are available to extract explanations for the predictions made through popular Python ML libraries, including sklearn, XGboost, and others. At the same time, explainability/ interpretability of features used in the ML models is another direction across which attention is being paid to further facilitate understanding of the predictions and the aspects of the input data affecting them.

B. Visualisation and Visual Exploration

Visualization and Visual Exploration can be defined in two separate directions. Visual exploration from the data point-of-view is the process of understanding the characteristics of the available data using appropriate visualization techniques. Visual exploration from the model point-of-view describes the process of explaining the model's behavior, i.e., understanding what a Machine Learning model has learned throughout the training phase, using appropriate visualization techniques. Both directions share the common characteristic of incorporating a suitable visualization technique for helping the user understand part of a Machine Learning process. Their difference is whether they focus on explaining the data or explaining the model. Visual exploration from the model point-of-view covers the visualization techniques that explain how a black-box model works and is thus tightly linked to the explainability aspects discussed.

C. MLOps

MLOps is a set of practices for building, deploying and managing Machine Learning (ML) systems. Its name is derived from ML and operations (Ops), and it can be thought of as the intersection between ML and DevOps (development operations) practices.

With the rapid growth in ML systems, MLOps has emerged as a solution that helps organizations successfully deploy ML models in production, manage risk, and ensure that applications are still in line with the business goals. MLOps practices aim to shorten development cycles, improve collaboration between teams, increase performance, scalability and security, and also increase return of investment of ML projects [7]. Another important area where MLOps plays a significant role in the ML lifecycle is model monitoring. Monitoring deployed models is crucial for continued provision of high quality ML services, and MLOps helps by monitoring model performance, monitoring metrics related to incoming data, detecting outliers and data drift, and also recognizing when models demand upgrades or retraining [8]. As such, it becomes evident that MLOps are relevant to all stages of AI-enabled pipelines and can significantly improve their reproducibility and robustness, accelerate their production serving and facilitate debugging. These aspects are important in all production-level applications of AI solutions and are thus also needed in the manufacturing domain to

ensure smooth integration of ML processes and outputs in decision making.

Collaboration aspects also emerge from the study of MLOps practices, as the steps that guide a data scientist's journey towards the successful delivery of an ML project are complemented by data engineers' contributions along the process, e.g. in model serving and monitoring.

D. Challenges

One of the most important outcomes of the state-of-the-art analysis is that AI pipelines, even when designed in a modular way to facilitate development, cannot be approached as a sequence of individual steps. There are many dependencies among the steps of ML development and deployment in production systems. Data exploration and understanding precedes model training and biases in training data, stemming from the initial raw data, will propagate in the system if unnoticed [9]. Governance audits in production environments are significantly facilitated when checkpoints for data distributions are in place and tracing erroneous predictions can be extremely difficult without safeguards in the feature extraction step. Explainability methods can reveal the most impactful features for a trained model and querying a model against specific selected instances can provide information on the way the model behaves and help the debugging process both during the experimentation and at the production phases. Experimentation is inherent in data science and is a process that spans across all steps from data understanding, to data exploration, to model exploration and testing.

This connection between the AI development steps and processes should be naturally reflected on the technical design of the underlying functionalities. Model performance in production can differ from that in the experimentation settings or it can gradually deteriorate due to numerous reasons, so establishing feedback loops and ensuring all involved stakeholders are aware that the process does not end after successfully training and deploying a model, is critical. At the same time, components in AI pipelines development are preferred to be modularized and containerized to promote reusability (with the exception of purely EDA tools, such as notebooks) [2] thus making the AI pipelines design process challenging.

Even though the importance of explainability is broadly accepted, it is not yet part of MLOps. With so many reported advantages, it may be anticipated that integrating explainability techniques, at least to some extent, in AI pipelines would be an already addressed need in the flourishing MLOps landscape. However, the state of the art review did not yield significant results. XAI and MLOps are two domains gaining attention from both the scientific and the commercial communities, but no established patterns and practices exist yet for their intersection.

Visualisation in other software development processes may be considered as a process closer to the end result, mainly addressing the end users, but reality in data analytics is different. From data exploration and outlier detection, to model training and experiments comparisons, to production performance evaluation and explainability insights, to training-production data skew monitoring, different visualisations are leveraged. Data scientists, data engineers and business users all require targeted and diverse visualisation functionalities to be available (pointing to the need for different libraries and technologies to be foreseen and

supported), as visual understanding, interpretation and even questioning of input data, models, and results is extremely powerful and significantly more intuitive for users.

Collaboration among the stakeholders involved in the different stages of the development and deployment of AI pipelines is crucial. It accelerates understanding, prevents mistakes, facilitates debugging and easier transition from experimentation to production serving and finally enables thorough performance evaluation and meaningful feedback loops. In reality, collaboration is a requirement and AI-enabled products cannot be put in production without it being satisfied. Making this collaboration easier across all steps in the most productive way for all involved actors is the real challenge. Workflow management systems allow multiple agents to work towards achieving a common goal by enabling communication between them. MLOps can be considered in this context as AI workflow management systems for automating the lifecycle of AI models. It improves communication and collaboration between business experts and data scientists to achieve effective management of the AI models lifecycle.

Notwithstanding the advantages gained from this collaboration, collaboration may also increase the level of complexity in the required functionalities. Starting from technical aspects such as granting access rights to different stakeholders for the various assets (datasets, models, pipelines, experiments, analysis results) to difficulties like ensuring that all relevant stakeholders have signed off on the model. Collaboration in terms of information flows can only have a positive effect, but collaborative decision making introduces new risks and challenges if involved stakeholders are not provided with the information they require in a comprehensible manner for their needs and background.

Finally, although the AI-specific aspects are important (e.g. AI development mentality, cross-team collaboration and all the AI pipeline development challenges already mentioned), designing and implementing the XMANAI AI bundles also brings the more traditional software development challenges. Scalability issues and in-memory analysis requirements should be studied and understood to put in place a robust technical solution.

III. FRAMEWORK DESIGN

The background review revealed a rich landscape of methods, algorithms, but also tools, and libraries that can be employed to design and develop ML-enabled products and services both in general and in the manufacturing sector in particular. At the same time, the analysis revealed the challenges associated with integrating ML results into decision making, delivering state of the art but also production-level AI pipelines that can be properly served and monitored in the real manufacturing environment settings, establishing fruitful and trustful interactions among involved stakeholders across the complete lifecycle of the ML-enabled processes. This section presents the design of a unified framework aspiring to help bring explainable AI pipelines into the everyday operations of the manufacturing domain in a trustworthy manner. The design spans across two dimensions:

- the aspects driving the high-level architecture decisions, which include (a) Explainability, (b) Domain Data Model, (c) Visualisation, and (d) Collaboration

- the actual designed and developed components that are shaped by the aforementioned drivers.

A. Explainability

Explainability mechanisms, both at the data and the model level, are by design tightly integrated in various steps of the developed XAI pipelines and their results will be made available in different “flavours” to the stakeholders that need them. Data scientists are expected to have different needs during model training and evaluation compared with business users trying to understand why a model made a certain prediction and what it would take for it to make a different one. Even when the same underlying need is shared (e.g., both technical and business users may need to comprehend what the important features that guide a model’s decisions are and to what direction they steer them), their different backgrounds should be considered when providing the respective explanation so that it can convey the right message to the users and ensure that they have the ability to interpret it correctly.

B. Domain Data Model

Having high-quality data to build upon is an indisputable requirement to create insightful AI pipelines, yet the importance of having common underlying structure and semantics for these data may not always be that obvious. Indeed, even without a common data model, data scientists can still explore, query and learn how to understand the available data, train and evaluate machine learning models etc. However, the availability of a data model can significantly facilitate and accelerate these processes and make them less error prone.

Using a common data model during data ingestion allows the stakeholders that have knowledge over the data (e.g. business users) to pass this information in an asynchronous manner to the teams that will be responsible for data analysis. Semantics will thus stay with the data, facilitating understanding for the data scientists even in the first steps of exploration. Spotting anomalies in the data, developing an intuition as to the expected distributions, creating meaningful visualisations, anticipating required transformations and thinking of potentially useful combinations, are among the processes that become easier based on this availability of data insights, thus accelerating everyday operations of data scientists when it comes to exploratory data analysis.

Going a step further, a data model is not only related to the input data, but can be also leveraged for derivative data generated during data pre-processing, feature engineering and finally results extraction from the AI models and analysis processes. In this way, data across the AI pipelines are enriched with semantics conveying to stakeholders what the data are about and how they can/should be handled. Having data that essentially “carry their meaning” directly contributes to the overall explainability of the XMANAI AI pipelines.

Numerous technical advantages also stem from ensuring that data conform to a common data model. Discrepancies and changes in the way input sources provide data, either due to errors or to performed updates, might go unnoticed and propagate to subsequent steps where debugging will be harder. Having a common data model allows the implementation of more advanced (in a way smarter) data validation rules, enhances and up to an extent guarantees data integrity and thus significantly facilitates production deployment and end-to-end monitoring of pipelines by data engineers. Furthermore, data manipulation operations in terms

of data manipulation can be enabled or disabled depending on the data types/units of the data being used. The same information can be leveraged in the way visualisations are configured, in the way feature extraction is performed and in the way ML models’ hyperparameters are configured.

Finally, having this common understanding of the data being used and enforcing certain actions, rules, quality and security tests based on commonly agreed upon structures, does not only facilitate the operations of each stakeholder role in XMANAI, but provides the foundations for a more productive collaboration among business users, data scientists and data engineers

After studying existing domain vocabularies, including ISO 10303, ISO 15926, X3D ontology, a graph data model has been defined that will be integrating in various steps of the XAI pipelines. Its current version comprises a total of 40 concepts spanning across different aspects, processes and entities of the manufacturing domain, including 3D Representation, Machine Monitoring, Market (Product and Customer), Production, Quality Control & KPI, Sensor data. Almost 200 properties and more than 110 relationships are defined to capture the underlying manufacturing knowledge in the form of associations among concepts. The XAI pipelines will leverage this targeted to the manufacturing domain data model across all the steps that this is possible, starting from fusing data explainability processes across the AI lifecycle. Indicative examples of the data model’s usage include leveraging the defined types and measurement units to help timely detect issues in the input data before these are propagated in training processes, using the available semantics to enable/disable feature creation and other data manipulation functionalities accordingly, making feature importance insights easier to comprehend by keeping the link to the overall structure and relationships among data. Integrating the data model in the AI lifecycle is also expected to contribute towards collaboration, as all stakeholders will have a common view and understanding on the data and models that drive the AI pipelines.

C. Visualisation

As highlighted in literature review, visualisation should not be considered a step in AI pipelines, as instead it constitutes an integral part of almost all its steps. Therefore, we approach visualisation, visual exploration and visual communication of results, explanations and overall findings as a constant need in our XAI pipelines development lifecycle throughout the process. All stakeholders involved in a pipeline will require visual support in the processes that are offered by the corresponding tools and will require different collaboration and interaction mechanisms, as they will each time focus on different aspects, i.e. on the data, the models, the experiments and the explanations. This will also be reflected clearly in the architecture presented in the next section, where the components offering visualization functionalities are presented.

D. Collaboration

The proposed XAI bundles provide a collaborative environment for data scientists, data engineers and business users to be able to work together to create, configure, train, evaluate and constantly monitor and refine AI pipelines in the manufacturing domain. Collaboration will be enabled across the complete flow of the AI lifecycle, thus contributing to reduce time in understanding data and identifying outliers,

accelerate model validation and debugging (also with the help of AI explainability methods), timely detect data and model drift or other issues in production. The proposed framework aims to deliver a solid collaborative experience around explainable AI models in manufacturing, not through a one-size-fit-all approach, but taking into consideration the background and needs of involved stakeholders in each step and also the processes to which they can/should contribute and the way this should be performed. This is the reason that in the developed XAI bundles, the main discussed entity is the AI pipeline as a whole and not only a trained AI model.

E. Architecture

The presented XAI bundles framework foresees, designs, and delivers eleven interacting components, shown in Figure 1 and briefly presented below.

Figure 1: XAI Bundles High-Level Architecture

The **Knowledge Graph Manager** is responsible for bringing semantic information to the XAI pipelines by ensuring that data used across the pipeline steps carry domain-specific meaning offered through the developed graph Data Model and thus directly contributing to data explainability. This component offers a visualization of and navigation into the Data Model, to facilitate the mapping of the harvested data to the data model as well as the modification of the data structure itself if necessary. The data that are used thus have an association with and definition of what the different concepts, properties and relationships between all of them are, which helps transmit the business knowledge to the data scientists in charge of delivering the ML models and then again to allow business users to more easily comprehend, and trust, the model outcomes through their link to the raw semantically enriched data. To account for the dynamic nature of the manufacturing domain, the Knowledge Graph Manager provides a set of functionalities to support the data model's lifecycle and allow its evolution through extension of the concepts, properties and relationships it supports.

The **Data Preparation Engine**, as the name reveals, provides the data processing functionalities which ensure that datasets can be appropriately filtered and transformed to be used as input in visualisations and/or in machine learning processes, i.e., as training data, as testing data or as actual data coming from the production environment to be used in

decision making. The component allows users to define and configure various data processing steps through its user interface in order to assemble the complete data manipulation chain, spanning from filters and dataset combinations to mathematical operations, to information extraction and feature engineering. For this purpose a set of data manipulation templates are offered, which after being configured by the users, are automatically transformed into python code and can be executed on the input (pandas dataframes) through the Execution & Orchestration Engine.

Experimentation is inherent in data science, both when it comes to data and to models. According also to the state of the art analysis, even in the context of MLOps and automation, notebooks are still considered valuable and established tools for data scientists and therefore an exception to the modularity paradigm in this case is part of the foreseen good practices. This is the role of the **Interactive Data Exploration and Experimentation Tool** which aims to provide (almost) full flexibility and freedom to data scientists to experiment with new technologies. Of course, this flexibility in experimentation brings limitations in terms of production deployment of the code generated through this process, as it will be explained in the corresponding section. The tool offers a set of predefined environments and templates which can be optionally used to accelerate the experimentation process. A predefined environment is a set of Python packages selected and pre-installed for a specific task. A template is a set of ready-to-use tools for a specific purpose. For example, the "Tabular Data Exploration" provides interactive tools to explore the characteristics of tabular data, helping users quickly gain an intuition for a dataset.

The **XAI Model Engineering Engine** provides the ML/DL model selection, configuration, training and application functionalities. The component allows users to train a model from scratch or re-train it from a previously completed experiment, configure its hyperparameters and validation strategy and visualize its training metadata. Closely related to it is the **XAI Model Explanations Engine** which powers the explainability methods' configuration, application and results (explanations) generation. The component is responsible for configuring the explanatory information that will be generated by the explainability tools selected by the user along with the predictions of ML/DL models. The component supports different explainability techniques selected through the state of the art analysis, and targeted visualisations for each explanation type and requesting user.

The **Experiment Tracking Engine** is based on MLflow and enables logging of experiments' metadata (performance metrics, corresponding hyperparameters and other artifacts) and performing comparisons in the performance of various trained models across selected dimensions.

The **XAI Model Guard** brings safeguarding mechanisms for the security and integrity of the trained AI models. Its main axes are the identification of potential adversarial (poisoning and evasion) attacks against the produced AI models, the assessment of the risks associated with such attacks and finally the presentation of the findings to the user so that the appropriate risk mitigation measures can be taken based on his/her knowledge on the trained AI model. The component incorporates several techniques and methods which can be leveraged as defence against pre-training (poisoning) attacks and post-training (evasion) attacks depending on the designed ML process. Finally, it safeguards

the integrity of the stored ML models through a sophisticated checksum-based mechanism that detects any possible alteration or corruption of the stored ML models.

The **Results Visualisation Engine** is responsible for enabling the end results generated by the AI pipelines to be appropriately visualised and communicated to the business users. The component provides the novel visualisation capabilities needed for the visual representation of the results generated from the performed data analysis.

The **Pipeline Designer** is in charge of the creation and management of the XAI pipelines and of enabling and coordinating the collaboration of different stakeholders (business experts, data scientists and data engineers) and team members across the various steps of the pipelines. The component offers a UI to allow users to graphically select, configure and connect steps from other components to create a chain of functionalities spanning across data retrieval, data manipulation and feature engineering, model training and application, creation of explainers and generation of explanations, and storing derivative assets. Discussion functionalities are offered at the pipeline and at the step level among stakeholders to facilitate collaboration.

The **Pipeline Serving and Monitoring Engine** is responsible for the deployment (with appropriate settings) of the pipelines that are suitable for usage in production and for monitoring their performance to provide insights regarding their operation.

The **Execution & Orchestration Engine** is the component responsible for scheduling an XAI pipeline and executing it according to the specified execution modality and in the predefined environment. In particular, the component is responsible for generating all the information needed in order to create the actual pipeline, starting from the corresponding configuration provided by the Pipeline Designer. The component supports two execution modalities: on the cloud platform and on-premise in a local environment. To make this possible, the component – by default designed to run in the cloud platform - can be replicated in a containerized environment on a local infrastructure, allowing for an offline execution that can be more in line with some company policies. During the execution of the XAI pipeline, the component collects low level execution traces related to each step of the pipeline and stores them in log files leveraged by the Pipeline Serving & Monitoring Engine to allow the user to perform real time monitoring of the pipeline status.

As a final note, the light outline in numerous blocks in Figure 1 denotes the visualization capabilities of the aforementioned component. In accordance with the described design principles, the Results Visualisation Engine is not the only component responsible for delivering visualisations. Instead, depending on their scope, the following components also offer targeted visualization capabilities: (a) the Interactive Exploration and Experimentation Tool naturally allows its users to configure and use their selected visualisation libraries, which are expected in this context to be oriented towards scientific visualisation (e.g. statistical data visualisations), (b) the XAI Model Explanations Engine utilises appropriate visual means to provide explanations to the requesting stakeholders - the nature of the visualisation here will probably differ according to the technical background of the requestor and the stage at which the request is performed (e.g. to comprehend a model's decision in production or to debug

the model when still in the training phase), (c) the Data Model Guard may also utilise visualisations, depending on the nature of the model that is being examined and the format of the data used during its training, and (d) the Experiment Tracking Engine, which offers targeted experiment comparison charts and visualisations to monitor model training performance, e.g. learning curves.

IV. CONCLUSION

A. Concluding Remarks

The presented framework constitutes a holistic approach to (a) create and manage AI pipelines with explainability features at the data level through a custom graph data model and at the model level through explainable machine learning techniques, (b) integrating these XAI pipelines and their outputs in the manufacturing decision making starting from the experimentation phase and going all the way until serving, validating and monitoring in production. Explainability aspects are brought to the spotlight and their successful inclusion across the developed components and their interactions has been challenging, considering also that established practices are not yet available. To achieve its goal, the framework foresees and enforces the collaboration of different domain stakeholders and offers functionalities to facilitate the interaction of expert users, data scientists and data engineers in the context of AI-enabled services development.

B. Future Work

The first release of the framework described in the current paper has been delivered according to the presented architecture and designed functionalities. Its evaluation in the context of four demonstrator scenarios stemming from real life manufacturing needs is currently ongoing. The four scenarios will validate the proposed architecture across diverse use cases which briefly include the holistic overview of the Ford production line and the automation of production planning, Whirlpool white goods demand forecasting, effective handling of stoppages at the CNHi production plant through predictive and collaborative maintenance and enabling smart semi-autonomous hybrid measurement planning in Unimetrik. Indicatively, in the case of Whirlpool central planners and inventory managers will assess the provided forecast not only through the result, but also by questioning its logic. As an example, feature importance calculated during model training will be examined from the perspective of the business users who will be able to check whether their intuition, developed through experience, matches the ML insights and will be given the opportunity to drill down to the pipelines' results to understand the model outcomes. What-if scenarios will be executed to shed light to the interdependencies and correlations among model features. These scenarios, which will under the hood execute the developed pipelines with different input data, will provide an additional way to business users to validate and ultimately learn to trust the results of the XAI pipelines. Each of the four use cases will help validate the framework as a whole, while also focusing on different explainability aspects and target users. The feedback gained through this process both directly from the demonstrator partners and indirectly through the collected logs of the framework's usage will be leveraged to improve the provided offerings and further adjust the developed components to the needs of the manufacturing domain and its stakeholders.

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